

ASSESSMENT OF THE RESERVE CAPACITY OF THE EXTERNAL RESPIRATION APPARATUS OF STUDENTS OF DIFFERENT SPORT SPECIALIZATIONS

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the functional analysis of the external respiration apparatus of students of different sports specializations. It examines the level of functional reserves of external respiration apparatus according to indices of power, mobilization and economical efficiency of male football players and athletes – above average – and of female football players and athletes – average. The assessment of the reserve capacity of external respiration apparatus may be used in the construction of the training process and will assist in the professional selection and sports orientation of students of the faculty of physical education.

Key words: external respiration, spirometry, the power reserve, the mobilization reserve, the economization reserve, football, field athletics.

Introduction

Research of the functional state of the external respiration system is one of the principal elements of the program of medico-biological control on the state of health of human beings who are regularly engaged in physical training. It is linked with the enormous role of the respiration system in the human body's adaptation to various types of physical obligations [2]. Aerobic productivity (especially in cyclical sports) is one of the most important factors that defines the working capacity and exercise tolerance of sportsmen. The level of aerobic productivity depends on the system of oxygen supply to the human body – the functional respiration system, which supplies oxygen from the environment to the acting tissues and performs the external respiration function, the function of gas transportation by blood (which is provided by the function of the blood circulating system) and the tissue respiration function [13]. The sportsman's body constantly experiences increasing mental and physical obligations, which influence the state of the functional respiration system that supplies the body with oxygen necessary for muscle activity. The external respiration system

limits the working capacity of the body to a considerable degree under the intensive obligations [1].

Analysis of recent research and publications

The increase of this problem in research during the last years has been caused by the necessity of appraising objectively the functional state and reserve possibilities of external respiration mechanism among children and teenagers involved in sport and by the drop in the state of health indices of various age groups. A considerable number of works are dedicated to the appraisal issue of reserve possibilities of external respiration of students due to the data of computer spirometry. Namely, N. Moskalenko and others devised the criteria of appraisal of reserve possibilities of external respiration of students [3]; E. Yevdokimov [5], I. Kotsan and others [7], investigated the peculiarities of external respiration apparatus under physical pressures and during the post pubertal period of ontogenesis; a number of scientists devised the model characteristics of functional state of the respiration system of karateka students [2], researched the indices of the respiratory system

of playing sports representatives, field athletes and cyclists [2-8, 10, 11].

However, to our mind, the issue of appraising the reserve possibilities of external respiration and the issue of improving the interpretation of the results of researches dedicated to the improvement of the planning of training process concerning pupils and students are studied insufficiently.

The research is carried out according to the plan of scientific research of the department of anatomy, physiology and valeology of Drogobych State Pedagogical University named after Ivan Franko.

Purpose: to summarize the scientific and methodical literature and data in the sphere of external respiration research of sportsmen. To analyze the basic indices of external respiration and its reserve possibilities that characterize the functional state of the respiration system of students with different sport specializations.

Materials and methods

The following methods were used for this research: analysis and generalization of scientific and methodical literature, and spirometry. The research was carried out according to the base of the department of anatomy, physiology and valeology of Drogobych State Pedagogical University named after Ivan Franko. 30 students (18-19 years of age) of Drogobych State Pedagogical University named after Ivan Franko took part in the experimental research. The spirometry indices were determined in the dominant equilibrium before the training activities. The computer-based complex "Micro QUARK" was used in order to appraise the functional state of external respiration of

sportsmen. Through the method of spirometry the following principal indices of external respiration mechanisms were defined: tidal volume (TV), respiration rate (RR), low voluntary ventilation (LVV), inspiratory reserve volume (IRV), vital capacity (VC), vital ratio (VR), forced vital capacity (FVC), peak expiratory flow (PEF), index Tiffani (FEV1/VC) and maximal voluntary ventilation (MVV). The majority of authors use these indices to analyze the functional state of external respiration apparatus. Each of the spirometric indices was compared with its predicted values, which were calculated with the formulae proposed by Y. Boldin depending on sex, age, stature and weight. The received data parameters were shown in predicted percentages.

The analysis of the received data was carried out with the help of computer programs "Microsoft Excel 2007" and "Statistics 6".

Results and discussion

Nowadays the majority of scientists consider VC to be one of the most important indices of the functional state of the external respiration system. VC also depends on sex, age, stature and the level of physical conditioning [1, 7]. The received data affirms the VC index of examined footballers is $5,068 \pm 0,18$ l.; field athletes – $5,22 \pm 0,44$ l. (tab.1), runners – $4,22 \pm 0,76$ l. [5] and volleyball players – $4166,9 \pm 98,6$ ml. [4], which corresponds in fact to the VC value of qualified football players and – $5,08 \pm 0,49$ l. [5]. Female VC index $3,264 \pm 0,2$ l. for football players and $3,451 \pm 0,13$ l. for field athletes and exceeds the indices of female field athletes according to I. Kotsan's data [7].

Table 1. External respiration indices of sportsmen of different specialization

	Male		Female	
	Football players (n=9)	Field athletes (n=6)	Football players (n=7)	Field athletes (n=8)
VC, l	$5,06 \pm 0,18$	$5,22 \pm 0,44$	$3,26 \pm 0,2$	$3,45 \pm 0,13$
ERV, l	$1,75 \pm 0,12$	$2,07 \pm 0,12$	$1,22 \pm 0,15$	$1,27 \pm 0,11$
IRV, l	$2,6 \pm 0,16$	$2,33 \pm 0,35$	$1,48 \pm 0,12$	$1,55 \pm 0,13$
TV, l	$0,71 \pm 0,05$	$0,8 \pm 0,09$	$0,55 \pm 0,08$	$0,62 \pm 0,07$
RR, per1 min	$13,4 \pm 0,34$	$12,5 \pm 0,74$	$15,4 \pm 0,45$	$14,6 \pm 0,34$
VR, ml/kg	$73,89 \pm 2,56$	$77,96 \pm 4,56$	$57,11 \pm 5,38$	$57,63 \pm 1,89$
MVV, l/min	$145,88 \pm 9,43$	$142,28 \pm 14,18$	$82,62 \pm 7,72$	$106,25 \pm 5,37$

TV MVV, l	0,815 ± 0,11	1,088 ± 0,2	0,47 ± 0,05	0,7 ± 0,04
weight, kg	68,89 ± 2,43	66,67 ± 2	58,28 ± 2,7	53,4 ± 7,19
stature, cm	176,4 ± 1,09	176 ± 1,8	160,85 ± 1,55	167,25 ± 2,4

To our mind, such differences from other authors require the development of the standards of predicted values, taking into account anthropometric data, length of service, mean of sport and sport qualification. That in return will cooperate in individual approach to training processes. One of the VC components is IRV, which accordingly in researched groups was: 2,6±0,16 l; 2,3±0,35 l; 1,487± 0,12 l; 1,55±0,13 l (tab.1).

The calculation of VR is considered to be a more informative index than VC calculations. The VR average values are 60 ml/kg for healthy males, 50 ml/kg for females, 68-70 ml/kg for male sportsmen, 57-60 for female sportsmen [9]. During the research it was found that the average VR index for male sportsmen (football players and field athletes) was: 73,89 2,56 ml/kg; 77,96 4,56 ml/kg, for female sportsmen – 57,11±5,38 ml/kg; 57,63 1,89 ml/kg accordingly. The results of the research prove the assumption about the positive changes of the static vital capacity as a consequence of sports activities, as far as the gained VR and VC values of sportsmen are higher than the values of non-exercising people.

To our mind, the received high VC value of sportsmen, apparently, is a result of adaptive changes of the respiration system (especially of males) because of years of sports training. According to the data of many authors [12, 13] the VC increase leads to the increase of respiration economization and the diffusive area of lungs. The increase of functional capacity of respiration muscles ensures the creation of a respiration current of high power. According to N. Moskalenko [3] the premises may be used as the indices of power reserve (of vital capacity (VC) values) and inspiratory reserve volume (IRV). Our researches showed that the high level of VC values was observed in males only. But, having analyzed the percentage of the VC indices to the predicated VC indices, we found out that VC value on average is 112,11±3,96% for male football players and 116,38±9,49% for male field athletes, which corresponds to a high level of power reserve (tab. 2). Accordingly, the VC indices for females are: 102,28±6,925%; 103,28±3,38%. The highest VC indices are observed in sportsmen who have a high level of exercise tolerance and the highest cardio respiratory productivity.

Table 2. Predicted values of external respiration apparatus of sportsmen

	Male		Female	
	Football players (n=9)	Field athletes (n=6)	Football players (n=7)	Field athletes (n=8)
pVC, ml	4519,09 ± 21,56	4488,31 ± 46,64	3197,28 ± 35,01	3338,06 ± 52,19
VC/pVC, %	112,11 ± 3,96	116,38 ± 9,49	102,34 ± 6,92	103,28 ± 3,38
pTV, ml	903,82 ± 4,31	897,66 ± 9,32	639,45 ± 7,01	667,73 ± 9,59
ERV, l	1,75 ± 0,12	2,075 ± 0,12	1,22 ± 0,15	1,27 ± 0,11
pERV, ml	1358,73 ± 6,46	1346,49 ± 13,99	959,18 ± 10,5	1001,6 ± 14,38
pIRV, ml	2259,54 ± 10,78	2244,15 ± 23,32	1598,64 ± 17,7	1669,3 ± 23,97
IRV, %	114,92 ± 6,99	103,84 ± 15,17	93,46 ± 8,05	93,26 ± 8,24
pMVV, l	112,46 ± 1,52	111,07 ± 2,12	98,79 ± 1,48	103,09 ± 2,30
MVV, %	126,44 ± 7,43	127,65 ± 11,26	84,02 ± 8,39	93,28 ± 8,24

Mobilization reserves determine the ability of the human body to mobilize the available morphofunctional resources of the respiration apparatus and realize them on a level with the maximal consumption of oxygen. We used the

maximal voluntary ventilation (MVV) to define the indices of mobilization reserves.

MVV is the volume of air that lungs receive during one minute under forced respiration. This index characterizes the verge of functional abilities of external respiration apparatus. The

higher the MVV is, the higher the potential physical capacity of sportsmen and the higher the chance of great sport achievement [3]. Our research showed (tab. 2) that MVV index for males under research was over 110% in comparison with the predicted values. The premises affirm the high level of mobilization. The MVV index for sportsmen (football players and field athletes) was on average $145,88 \pm 9,43$ l/min, $142,28 \pm 14,18$ l/min. According to the authors for handball and football players, the MVV values were established in the range of 127-152 l/min [5]. That is why the received result indicates the high functional mobilization reserves of the external respiration system of male sportsmen under research. The MVV for female field athletes was $106,25 \pm 5,37$ l/min, for female football players $82,62 \pm 7,72$ l/min, and the mobilization reserve was 93,28 8,24% and 84,02 8,39% accordingly.

Economization reserves are characterized by the coefficient of the efficiency of respiration function, its power value, and are ensured by the diffusive capacity of the lungs, the ratio of ventilation to the pulmonary bloodstream in different parts, the increase of alveolar and ventilation gradient and the rate of oxygen utilization in the tissues. The economization of the functioning of the respiration system according to this method can be assessed only in the physiological dominant equilibrium with the help of respiration rate (RR) and tidal volume (TV). While researching the respiration in dominant equilibrium, we have established the TV $0,71 \pm 0,05$ l for male football players, $0,80 \pm 0,09$ l for male field athletes, $0,55 \pm 0,08$ l and $0,62 \pm 0,07$ l for female sportsmen accordingly. It is known that RR (of sportsmen) under tranquil respiration tends to be reduced, which simultaneously causes the increase of TV. Slow and deep respiration according to many

authors [1], reduces considerably the power inputs of the organism while breathing in dominant equilibrium.

Using the assessment criteria of reserve capacities of external respiration apparatus of sportsmen of different sports specializations, we received the following results in points, which enable the assessment of the power reserve for 4,33 points for male sportsmen; mobilization reserve - 4,44 points for male football players and 4,33 points for field athletes; economization reserve - 3,44 points for male football players and 3,66 points for field athletes. The received points of reserve capacities of external respiration apparatus of female sportsmen were lower: power reserve 3,85 points for football players and 4,12 points for field athletes; mobilization reserve - 2,42 and 3,87 points accordingly; economization reserve - 2,71 and 2,87 points accordingly (fig. 1).

Comparison of the results of all types of reserves allows us to assess the reserve capacity of external respiration apparatus of sportsmen of different sports specializations. According to table 3, the general level of reserve capacities of external respiration apparatus is 4,07 0,14 for male football players, 4,11 0,21 for male field athletes, which corresponds to the above the average level of reserve capacities of external respiration apparatus. The reserve indices for female sportsmen are 3,0 0,36 and 3,62 0,21 accordingly (average level). To our mind, this has to do with the degree of functional capacities' change under the influence of sports training. The higher the degree of sports training, the lower the level of being trained. The training degree of sportsmen of the same age and sex group is determined with the initial level of functional indices, which change in different ways under the influence of training.

Figure 1. Reserve capacities of external respiration apparatus

The higher the change of these indices, the lower the initial level of functional preparedness. There are 2 reactions to adaptation: training and

activation. The first consists of 3 stages: training, rebuilding and the state of being trained [7].

Table 3. Assessment of reserve capacities of external respiration apparatus

	Male		Female	
	Football players (n=9)	Field athletes (n=6)	Football players (n=7)	Field athletes (n=8)
Average level of reserve capacities	4,07±0,14	4,11±0,21	3,0±0,36	3,62±0,21
Level of reserves	Above the average		average	

It was established that the general tendency is to increase the power of the functional respiration system in dominant equilibrium regardless of sex. However, because of the anatomic and physiologic peculiarities of the female body: less muscle mass, a less powerful respiration system, the stage-by-stage quickness of oxygen delivery and its utilization occurs in the female body in quite a different way than it does in males. The quickness of stage-by-stage oxygen delivery is lower in sportswomen even of the highest level of sport qualification, than it is in non-trained males [12, 13]. Thus, sport training on the professional level upraises the power of the functional system of external respiration.

Conclusions

The received indices of external respiration of students of the department of physical

education either correspond to or exceed the average normative values of healthy people in dominant equilibrium and of representatives of different sport activities. These indices can be used to improve and adjust the training process. It is established that the general level of the functional reserve of external respiration apparatus of male football players and field athletes is above the average; of female football players and field athletes – average.

Perspectives for further research. It is necessary to develop the predicted value standards of external respiration indices for sportsmen, which would take into account the anthropometric data, experience, type of sport activity, sport qualification in order to facilitate the customized approach to the training process.

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